

Programmable Security for 6G Mobile Networks: the vision of HORSE and MARE projects

Fabrizio Granelli
Information Engineering and Computer Science
CNIT & University of Trento
Trento, Italy
fabrizio.granelli@unitn.it

Eva Rodriguez, Xavier Masip-Bruin
CRAAX and
Univeritat Politecnica de Catalunya
Barcelona, Spain
evar@ac.upc.edu, xavier.masip@upc.edu

Ioannis Vasalos, George Xilouris
Institute of Informatics and Telecommunications
National Centre for Scientific Research "DEMOKRITOS" (NCSR)
15310 Agia Paraskevi, Greece
ivasalos@iit.demokritos.gr, xilouris@iit.demokritos.gr

Abstract—In 6G, effective protection mechanisms must be inherently cross-layer and adaptive. In this context, the HORSE and MARE projects align with this vision by proposing an adaptable and extensible approach based on a 6G service provisioning platform. This approach introduces a novel security plane built upon a well-defined set of open and programmable security functions, delivered as enablers within the 6G architecture. It operates transparently across multi-domain and multi-stakeholder environments, while efficiently handling emerging threats. As such, it enables the dynamic orchestration of security strategies to efficiently address novel and evolving attacks.

Index Terms—6G Mobile Networks, Security, Programmable Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution toward sixth-generation (6G) communication systems is expected to enable unprecedented levels of connectivity, intelligence, and service integration, supporting applications such as immersive extended reality, autonomous systems, and large-scale cyber-physical infrastructures. While these advancements promise significant societal and economic benefits, they also introduce profound security challenges that must be addressed from the early stages of system design. In contrast to previous generations, 6G networks are envisioned as highly heterogeneous, deeply integrated with artificial intelligence, and extensively reliant on distributed architectures, thereby redefining the traditional assumptions underpinning network security.

One of the primary challenges in securing 6G systems arises from the substantial expansion of the attack surface. The proliferation of connected devices, ranging from resource-constrained sensors to highly capable edge nodes, combined with the integration of terrestrial, aerial, and satellite networks, creates a complex and highly distributed ecosystem. This increased heterogeneity not only broadens the number of potential entry points for adversaries but also complicates the enforcement of consistent security policies across diverse domains and technologies.

In addition, the pervasive adoption of softwarization and virtualization paradigms, such as network function virtualization and software-defined networking, introduces new classes of vulnerabilities. While these technologies enable flexibility, scalability, and rapid service deployment, they also shift critical network functionalities into software layers that may be more susceptible to misconfigurations, software bugs, and exploitation. The dynamic nature of virtualized environments further exacerbates these risks, as network functions can be instantiated, migrated, or scaled in real time, potentially creating transient security gaps that adversaries can exploit.

Finally, the security landscape of 6G is characterized by the emergence of evolving and increasingly unpredictable attack types.

These challenges highlight the necessity for a fundamental rethinking of security in 6G networks, emphasizing proactive, adaptive, and intelligence-driven approaches capable of operating in highly dynamic and complex environments.

This paper presents the approach proposed by two SNS JU research projects, HORSE and MARE, their architectures and modules, and some relevant achieved results.

The structure of the paper is as follows: this section introduces the topic of the paper, while the next section provides an overview of the literature on the topic of security in 6G. Then, two more sections describe in brief the approaches followed into two SNS JU projects, HORSE and MARE, respectively. Finally, Section V provides an extensive discussion of the achievements and results, and how they can be used in 6G mobile networks, while Section VI concludes the paper with some final remarks.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The evolution from 5G to 6G represents a fundamental shift toward a hyper-connected ecosystem in which communications, computing, and intelligent systems are deeply integrated. This evolution extends far beyond incremental performance gains, reshaping how connectivity is defined and delivered.

However, the scale, complexity, and accelerated pace of this transformation introduce significant challenges in ensuring robust security and privacy. Key issues include the protecting sensitive data, ensuring the reliability of ultra-low latency services, detecting emerging and previously unknown threats, and maintaining the integrity of increasingly distributed network infrastructures. Moreover, 6G is envisioned as an open and highly flexible platform, characterized by open interfaces and the tight integration of diverse enabling technologies. While this openness facilitates dynamic service orchestration and accelerates the deployment of new applications, it simultaneously broadens the attack surface beyond that of earlier network generations, introducing new vulnerabilities that must be carefully managed. In the literature, several works analyse the emerging threat landscape for 6G networks [1] [2]. Most of these studies adopt a layered perspective, typically aligned with the Hexa-X end-to-end architecture [3] and future 6G IoT-enabled frameworks [4]. Within this context, security challenges in 6G are commonly categorized into three primary layers: physical, connection, and service. This abstraction provides a structured approach to understanding vulnerabilities by associating specific threats to their corresponding architectural domains. Consequently, it enables network operators and system developers to more effectively identify, analyse, and mitigate attacks by considering the underlying protocols and enabling technologies that influence each layer. In a similar manner, security solutions have been proposed and classified according to these layers, as surveyed in [5] [6]. These approaches encompass specialized mechanisms tailored to specific layers or use cases. In addition, advanced Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) [7] have been developed to operate in distributed and highly dynamic environments, while of deep learning (DL) techniques have been increasingly adopted to detect sophisticated and previously unseen attacks [8]. However, these studies highlight that effective protection mechanisms must be inherently cross-layer and adaptive. In this context, the HORSE and MARE projects align with this vision by proposing an adaptable and extensible approach based on a 6G service provisioning platform. This approach introduces a novel security plane built upon a well-defined set of open and programmable security functions, delivered as enablers within the 6G architecture. It operates transparently across multi-domain and multi-stakeholder environments, while efficiently handling emerging threats. As such, it enables the dynamic orchestration of security strategies to efficiently address novel and evolving attacks.

III. SECURITY IN HORSE

In the security challenging context described before, the HORSE project appeared as an EU SNS-JU initiative running from 2022 to 2025, aimed at proposing a holistic, human-centric and sustainable security framework for end-to-end 6G systems, securing the lifecycle management in multi-stakeholder and multi-domain resource environments [10].

Conceptually, HORSE sits on two fundamental pillars: i) Threats identification and modeling, in order to acquire as

many information as possible about threats and potential attackers leveraging the work done in the MITRE ATT&CK Framework ¹, and the deployment of Network Digital Twins (NDT) to maximize the chances for specific security actions to be properly deployed [9], and; ii) AI- Enabled solutions for security enhancement and threat mitigation, facilitating the deployment of both proactive approaches and analysis of potential impacts that will facilitate prevention instead of mitigation actions as well as guarantee no action will be deployed without having guarantees about its performance. This two pillars turn into tangible and significant innovations that may summarized into three specific roadmaps: i) deploy a security provisioning strategy supporting reactive but also proactive approaches, the latter adding a novel dimension in how security is addressed, through the integration of ML, cybersecurity and Digital Twins, assigning a confidence score to each detection event, what indeed will allow for a more adaptive and intelligent cybersecurity strategy; ii) design and develop a “what-if loop”, leveraging NDTs and the early modeling of attacks, responsible for analyzing what the impact a potential action may have before being deployed, and; iii) deploy a compliance assessment strategy, responsible for validating policies compliance and thus guaranteeing that any policy (privacy, performance, sustainability, etc.) is met before any action is implemented. The innovations proposed in HORSE are built on a set of functional blocks turning into the functional architecture described in Figure 1, depicting the main components and highlighting their interfaces and communication flows. The HORSE solution, through the proposed architecture provides 4 key functionalities HORSE understands should properly guarantee security provisioning in 6G ecosystems, namely: (i) data collection and preprocessing, (ii) threat detection, (iii) threat prediction and analysis, (iv) recommendation, (v) deployment.

Next, these functionalities are briefly introduced:

- Data Collection and Preprocessing, encompasses three main architectural blocks: i) The Smart Monitoring (SM) component, responsible for continuously gathering data, coming from the underlying infrastructure, the distinct domain orchestrators, and the resource utilization linked to the 6G services; ii) The Pre-processing, responsible for coordinating large-scale and heterogeneous sources within a unified, extensible data framework, and; iii) The Policies and Data Governance (PAG), responsible for providing the mechanisms required to define and enforce data policies for all HORSE information, covering anonymization, access control, privacy-preserving rules, and data retention.
- Threat Detection, encompasses one single element, the Detector and Mitigation Engine (DEME), responsible for running threat detection directly in the real infrastructure, identifying attack scenarios capable of causing disruption across significant portions of the network, and providing

¹MITRE ATT&CK. Available: <https://attack.mitre.org>

Fig. 1. HORSE functional architecture.

high-level mitigation guidance, particularly for threats requiring immediate response.

- Threat Prediction Impact Analysis, putting together two main functional blocks: i) the Sandboxing (SAN) builds an emulated "network-in-network" environment, mirroring realistic network scenarios, aiming at supporting experimentation with no need to disrupt the operational network, and; ii) the Early Modeling (EM) feeds the emulated environment built on the SAN with all the structural and behavioral models required to trigger the experiments, including the description of potential threats and attacks, their expected impact on the 6G system, and the projected impacts of enforcing mitigation or preventive actions. In this context, two different analysis are carried out in SAN, considering two NDT implementations, the first named as Prediction Prevention NDT, predicts anomalies and threats within the emulated environment and the second named as Impact Analysis NDT, estimates the impact of enforcing either mitigation or preventive strategies on the emulated context before they are applied to the real 6G infrastructure.
- Recommendation, encompasses three functional blocks: i) The Distributed Trustable AI Engine (DTE), responsible for producing high-level mitigation and prevention strategies expressed as intents; ii) The Common Knowledge Base (CKB), storing and managing information such as vulnerabilities, attack patterns, mitigation strategies, and preventive actions, and; iii) The Intent Based Interface (IBI), responsible for translating high-level intents into executable workflows, while validating the proposed intents against relevant policies, using ML techniques, and the outcome of the Impact Analysis NDT to ensure that the proposed mitigation or preventive actions is

compliant with acceptable impact scores.

- Deployment, final functionality putting together four functional blocks: i) The Reliability, Trust and Resilience (RTR), responsible for defining the mitigation and preventive actions to be applied by the ePEM, delivered as Ansible security playbooks derived from the workflows produced by the IBI.; ii) The Compliance Assessment (CAS), guaranteeing ePEM's enforcement policies to comply with HORSE policies and meet regulatory requirements (e.g., 3GPP and ENISA guidelines); iii) The end-to-end (E2E) secure connectivity manager (ePEM), serving as an Operations Support System (OSS), executes mitigation and preventive strategies defined by RTR across the infrastructure, and; iv) The Domain Orchestrator Connectors (DOC), responsible for orchestrating the deployment across all 6G network segments.

IV. SECURITY IN MARE

A. Overview

The MARE (Programmable, Modular and Disaggregated Security Plane for 6G Ecosystems) project addresses one of the most pressing challenges of next-generation mobile networking: the need for a comprehensive, adaptive, and programmable security framework capable of defending heterogeneous 6G infrastructures against an evolving threat landscape. Unlike previous generations, 6G networks are expected to integrate cloud-native disaggregation, AI-driven intelligence, extended edge deployments, open API exposure, and multi-domain convergence—all of which dramatically expand the attack surface and demand security mechanisms that are fundamentally modular, composable, and proactive. The MARE Security Plane is designed around four core architectural principles: (i) atomic composability through

DOTs, whereby fine-grained security primitives serve as reusable and interoperable building blocks; (ii) separation of functional layers, which enforces a clear distinction between core intelligence, infrastructure mediation, and external interaction; (iii) proactive programmable validation via pre-assessment environments, enabling security actions to be tested before live deployment; and (iv) flexible orchestration through Security Function composition, allowing context-sensitive and adaptive responses to emerging threats. These principles are directly aligned with the modular, open, and AI-driven security paradigm advocated by the HEXA-X-II 6G blueprint.

B. MARE Security Plane Architecture

The MARE Security Plane is structured as a three-tier layered architecture (Fig. 2). The Cybersecurity Core is the

Fig. 2. MARE functional architecture.

central intelligence hub, comprising two functional blocks. The Security and Privacy Engine (SEPE) manages the full life-cycle of security assets: atomic primitives called DOTs (tools, algorithms, monitoring probes, enforcement components) are catalogued in a DOTs Repository and dynamically composed by the Security Functions Composer (SFC) into higher-level Security Functions (SFs). The Adaptive Security and Privacy Orchestrator (ASPO) then selects and deploys the appropriate SF using a MITRE ATT&CK-informed knowledge base, a recommender module, and a playbook designer that formalizes responses into machine-executable workflows. The Pre-assessment Stress Testing Environment (PASTE) complements SEPE by validating candidate SFs before live enforcement across three contexts: simulation (Open5GS/USERANSIM), emulation via Network Digital Twins (NDTs), and real infrastructure testbeds.

The Abstraction Layer bridges the heterogeneous 6G infrastructure and the Cybersecurity Core. Its four components—Attack Surface Identification (ASI), Telemetry, Systems Characterization, and System Aggregation—transform low-level, multi-domain data into structured, security-relevant representations consumed by SEPE and PASTE. The Interface Layer exposes the Security Plane to operators

and external systems through Visual Mapping (ViMa) for real-time security state visualization, an IBN Manager for intent-based interaction, standardized API/Connectors for third-party integration, Security Service Level Agreements (SSLAs) for policy governance, and an open Service Repository for collaborative SF development.

C. Threat Landscape and Thematic Areas

MARE structures the 6G security problem space into five Thematic Areas (TAs), each targeting a distinct facet of the 6G ecosystem. For each TA, specific attack scenarios are formalized, using a common threat analysis methodology that includes attack scenario definition, mapping to the MITRE ATT&CK framework, CVSS severity scoring, impact analysis, and mitigation recommendations.

- TA1 – Disaggregation with a cloud-native approach (including O-RAN): addresses threats arising from network infrastructure disaggregation. The scope of the attacks cover O-RAN critical attack detection, AI/ML-aided threat protection for the 6G Core, and full-plane detection of internal attacks on network control elements.
- TA2 – Intelligence at scale, AI adoption, data analytics: addresses the security risks introduced by AI-driven network intelligence. The scope of the attacks include Man-in-the-Middle attacks targeting AI models, IBN data and intent tampering detection, NWDAF data poisoning, trustworthy AI operations in the network and Secure Network Digital Twin protection.
- TA3 – Heterogeneous resources, far edge and extensive edge usage: targets DDoS attacks originating from extended-edge (X-Edge) devices.
- TA4 – Network openness and exposure APIs: addresses threats to network capability exposure APIs, focusing on sensitive data leakage and secure API management.
- TA5 – System convergence: Network of Networks architecture tackles cross-domain security in federated multi-network environments, including MitM, API spoofing, and data tampering in inter-network communications.

D. Operational Security Workflows

The MARE Security Plane operates through two canonical workflows that govern the interactions between its architectural components.

Threat Detection Workflow. This reactive workflow is initiated by the Telemetry component, which continuously feeds infrastructure monitoring data to SEPE. Upon detecting an anomaly, SEPE generates a threat alert—including attack type, affected components, and confidence indicators—and forwards it to ASPO. ASPO queries its knowledge base, generates an orchestration playbook, and instructs the SFC to compose the required SF. The composed SF is then submitted to the PAV module, which validates its effectiveness against SSLA-derived policies. Upon successful validation, the SF is deployed and enforced in the live 6G infrastructure.

Threat Prediction Workflow. This proactive workflow is driven by the PASTE module. A threat prediction function runs continuously within PAV, analysing telemetry data to estimate the probability of an impending attack. When a threat is predicted, PAV queries SSLA policies to assess the potential impact on the infrastructure and triggers ASPO to generate a preventive orchestration playbook. The resulting SF is validated using a Network Digital Twin as the assessment context. Only upon successful NDT-based validation is the preventive SF approved and enforced in the production infrastructure.

V. DISCUSSION AND LESSONS LEARNED FOR 6G

A. Overall summary of achievements

At a high level, the two projects attack the same 6G security problem from different architectural angles.

HORSE treats security as part of an AI-assisted, closed-loop management and orchestration system for a highly distributed 6G/edge/cloud environment. Its final architecture is organized around three main blocks: the Intent-Based Interface (IBI), Platform Intelligence (PIL), and AI Secure and Trustable Orchestration (STO). In practice, HORSE combines monitoring, preprocessing, threat detection/mitigation, sandboxing with network-digital-twin support, an AI engine, a knowledge base for attacks and mitigations, orchestration/enforcement, and compliance assessment. The goal is not just to detect threats, but to translate high-level intents into mitigation workflows and execute them across RAN, transport, core, edge, and cloud domains. That makes HORSE especially strong for operational security in 6G: continuous monitoring, prediction, “what-if” analysis, assisted decision-making, and automated response.

MARE, by contrast, is more explicit about building a dedicated 6G security plane. Its central idea is that 6G security should be modular, programmable, and composable, rather than embedded only as fixed functions inside the network. MARE’s architecture is described as three layers: a Cybersecurity Core, where basic security primitives called DOTs are composed into Security Functions and orchestrated; an Abstraction Layer, which collects monitoring data and maps the attack surface; and an Interface Layer, which exposes the security plane to operators, service providers, and developers. It also includes a pre-assessment environment using simulation, emulation, and real infrastructure to evaluate countermeasures before deployment.

So, in brief:

- HORSE = security-aware management/orchestration architecture with AI-driven detection, prediction, compliance, and actuation.
- MARE = programmable security-plane architecture where security services themselves are modular building blocks that can be composed on demand.

That means they are two complementary projects addressing the same issue of 6G security. HORSE is focused on a secure zero-touch operational framework; MARE is focused on a native, reusable security substrate for 6G services and domains.

B. Open Challenges

First, both architectures assume very rich observability across heterogeneous domains. HORSE needs data from infrastructure, orchestrators, services, and UEs; MARE’s Abstraction Layer needs enough telemetry to build an attack-surface view and support dynamic composition of security functions. In real deployments, that means standardized telemetry, common semantics, and trustworthy cross-domain data sharing are critical. Without them, the intelligence layer or security plane becomes fragmented.

Second, both assume closed-loop automation that is safe enough for security actions. HORSE explicitly turns intents into mitigation workflows and enforcement; MARE wants orchestration of security functions in response to evolving threats. The challenge is that false positives, policy conflicts, or incorrect AI inferences can have operational consequences as serious as the attacks themselves. That creates a need for explainability, policy validation, staged rollout, and rollback mechanisms. HORSE partly addresses this through compliance assessment and “what-if” or sandboxing; MARE addresses it through pre-assessment and attack modelling.

Third, there is a major multi-domain trust problem. Both projects target environments spanning multiple stakeholders and technology segments. MARE explicitly emphasizes multi-domain and multi-stakeholder provisioning; HORSE includes domain orchestrator connectors across RAN, transport, core, edge, and cloud. In practice, composing security services or enforcing mitigations across administrative boundaries requires identity, attestation, authorization, policy federation, and liability models that are much harder than single-operator automation.

Fourth, both bring AI into the security loop, which adds AI security and governance challenges. MARE explicitly lists threats to AI-based systems and digital twins among its targets; HORSE uses distributed trustable AI and LLM-supported mitigation knowledge. That raises issues like model poisoning, drift, provenance of training data, robustness of inference, and whether operators can trust automatically generated recommendations.

Fifth, both rely on digital twins, emulation, or pre-assessment, which is powerful but difficult. The more critical the use case, the more accurate the twin has to be. Security validation in a twin is only as good as the fidelity of the telemetry, models, and attack assumptions used to build it. That is particularly hard in 6G because compute, radio, edge, AI pipelines, and applications are tightly coupled.

C. Does 6G provide all the required interfaces and functionalities to deploy these solutions?

Not yet, at least not as a complete, mature, standardized set. As of now, 3GPP Release 20 includes preliminary 6G study work; it is not yet a fully frozen 6G architecture with all the interfaces these projects would need for portable deployment across vendors and domains. What exists today is a partial foundation, mostly inherited from 5G and 5G-Advanced and adjacent management standards.

5G already provides a Service-Based Architecture in the core, with service-based interfaces and network capability exposure. It also provides analytics functions and exposure mechanisms relevant to data-driven automation, as well as frameworks for network capability exposure. ETSI ZSM is advancing intent-driven, zero-touch management and cross-domain orchestration concepts that fit particularly well with architectures like HORSE.

Those existing capabilities are enough to prototype or partially deploy pieces of HORSE- and MARE-like systems on top of 5G-Advanced and cloud-native platforms. However, they are not enough by themselves to guarantee end-to-end deployment of the full project visions.

The main gaps are the following.

First, standardized security-plane interfaces are missing. MARE assumes programmable composition of security primitives and clean interfaces between the security plane, infrastructure abstraction, and external consumers. Today, there is no widely adopted equivalent of a universal security plane API.

Second, intent semantics are still immature across domains. HORSE depends heavily on intents flowing into orchestration and mitigation logic. Interoperable semantics for security intents across RAN, transport, core, cloud, and third-party edge domains are still not fully settled.

Third, cross-domain trust, attestation, and evidence exchange are not sufficiently standardized. Both projects need trustworthy interactions across multiple domains and stakeholders. Concrete interoperable mechanisms for shared evidence, trust scores, attestation, and policy federation are still evolving.

Fourth, AI-native security control loops need more standard support. Both projects assume that AI outputs can trigger or guide enforcement. Standard interfaces for AI model lifecycle, assurance, provenance, and safe actuation in telecom control loops are still incomplete.

Fifth, digital-twin interfaces and fidelity requirements are not mature enough. Both projects rely on simulation and emulation for validation, but standard APIs and data models for coupling operational networks with security testing twins remain largely research topics.

Indeed, currently, 6G does not yet provide all the required interfaces and functionalities in a fully standardized, deployment-ready form. What it provides today is a promising base, including service-based architectures, exposure mechanisms, analytics, and zero-touch management concepts, along with a broader architectural direction in which security and trust are expected to be native.

The HORSE and MARE projects provide some useful proofs and directions to incorporate novel and emerging topics in cybersecurity, and hopefully provide significant contributions to support 6G to deploy its full potential.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has discussed how the architectures proposed in the SNS JU HORSE and MARE projects address security in 6G from two complementary perspectives. HORSE approaches

security as an integral part of an AI-driven, closed-loop management and orchestration framework, enabling continuous monitoring, predictive analysis, and automated mitigation across heterogeneous domains. MARE, on the other hand, promotes the concept of a programmable and composable security plane, where modular security functions can be dynamically instantiated and orchestrated to match evolving threats and service requirements. Together, these approaches illustrate a shift from static, built-in security mechanisms toward adaptive, software-driven, and intelligence-assisted security architectures that are more aligned with the complexity and dynamism expected in 6G systems.

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